

SOLVING THE BEST PROJECT SELECTION PROBLEM BY USING FUZZY MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION MAKING METHOD

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ABSTRACT

While the project continues, the slightest delay in the critical path can cause major problems. For this reason, in determining the critical path, there may be many criteria to be considered, not just time or cost. Multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) techniques are used in cases where many criteria are taken into account. In the most general sense, the decision problem can be defined as the selection of the most appropriate option from a set of options according to at least one objective or criterion. Decision making is one of the most important activities for businesses. This process requires enormous amounts of time and cost. Accordingly, the elements of a decision problem can be listed as decision makers, options, criteria, results, environment and priorities of the decision maker. Therefore, in this issue we apply fuzzy MCDM method to selection the best project. This problem consist of four alternatives (projects) and four criteria. The results show effectiveness of this method.

Keywords: Multi-criteria decision making, project, contract period, resection in degree of contractor, profit, project risks.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to its many benefits, including its availability, minimal greenhouse gas emissions, and the trend toward cost reduction, renewable energies are becoming more and more popular [1]. Considering all relevant factors that influence decision-making is essential for energy projects to reach their desired goals. Multicriteria Decision Making (MCDM) techniques are a dependable and effective means of formulating policies and arriving at the best possible conclusion. When ranking the options, these methods consider the significant variables and their relative weight. This article concentrates on studies about the applications of MCDM approaches to selecting renewable energy technologies, as the results of these methods rely on the criteria and algorithm utilized. The current paper's goal is to extract the essential criteria for usage in renewable energy system decision-making. Furthermore, strategies used to enhance the effectiveness of MCDM techniques as tools for decision-making are illustrated. Based on this review study, the majority of decision-making studies incorporate technical, economic, and environmental aspects. To make decisions that are more trustworthy, several research have also taken into account additional factors including risk and social factors. Some concepts, such combining various approaches and applying fuzzy sets rather than crisp sets to increase MCDM method performance and lower uncertainty, are included in the evaluated studies [1].

[2] attempts to enhance pharmaceutical businesses' project portfolio selection procedures in the face of uncertainty by combining the AHP and VIKOR methods, two Multicriteria Decision Making (MCDM) techniques, in a fuzzy environment.

[3] employs Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) to construct a business plan aimed at lowering the cost of products, enhancing competitiveness, emphasizing production planning based on actual operating capacity and adaptability to market fluctuations,

optimizing workforce productivity in technology workshops, cutting expenses and inventory, and concentrating on generating a large number of petrochemical products and high-value products.

For the organisation to succeed as a whole, choosing the appropriate materials supplier is crucial. Finding a suitable supplier and evaluating them are difficult tasks that require the decision-maker to take into account both qualitative and quantitative information. When dealing with complicated selection problems involving numerous criteria and options, multi-criteria decision making models are a useful tool, particularly when dealing with qualitative variables. In order to assess and choose the best supplier in the oil industry, the author suggests an MCDM model that incorporates the Supply Chain Operation Reference (SCOR) model, the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) method, and the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). The SCOR model establishes the evaluation criteria for potential suppliers, the AHP model determines the weight of each criterion based on the opinion of an expert, and the DEA model is used for evaluating providers at the end. The results of the model's implementation indicate that DMU_01, DMU_04, and DMU_10 are the top suppliers, as determined by the decision-making unit. A Multi-Criteria Decision Making model for supplier assessment and selection in oil production projects is presented in this research. Additionally, this study offers helpful recommendations for supplier selection procedures in other sectors of the economy.

In this article we use fuzzy TOPSIS method for solving the best project selection problem.

2. STATEMENT AND SOLUTION OF THE PROBLEM

The decision matrix of consider problem consist of four project (alternatives) and four criteria: contract period, resection in degree of contractor, project risks, profit (see Table 1). For solving the algorithm of fuzzy TOPSIS method is used [4].

Table 1.

Decision matrix

weight	0,25			0,2			0,29			0,26		
	Contract Period			Resection in degree of contractor			Project risks			Profit		
Project 1	10,8	12	13,2	3,6	4	4,4	5,4	6	6,6	7,2	8	8,8
Project 2	9	10	11	1,8	2	2,2	6,3	7	7,7	5,4	6	6,6
Project 3	9,9	11	12,1	3,6	4	4,4	8,1	9	9,9	4,5	5	5,5
Project 4	8,1	9	9,9	0,9	1	1,1	6,3	7	7,7	0,9	1	1,1

The normalized fuzzy decision matrix (see Table 2) [4]

Table 2.

NFDM

weights	0,25			0,2			0,29			0,26		
	Contract Period			Resection in degree of contractor			Project risks			Profit		
Project 1	0,82	0,91	1,00	0,82	0,91	1,00	0,55	0,61	0,67	0,82	0,91	1,00
Project 2	0,68	0,76	0,83	0,41	0,45	0,50	0,64	0,71	0,78	0,61	0,68	0,75
Project 3	0,75	0,83	0,92	0,82	0,91	1,00	0,82	0,91	1,00	0,51	0,57	0,63
Project 4	0,61	0,68	0,75	0,20	0,23	0,25	0,64	0,71	0,78	0,10	0,11	0,13

The weighted normalized fuzzy decision matrix (see Table 3).

Table 3.

The weighted NFDM

	Contract Period			Resection in degree of contractor			Project risks			Profit		
Project 1	0,205	0,227	0,250	0,164	0,182	0,200	0,158	0,176	0,193	0,213	0,236	0,260
Project 2	0,170	0,189	0,208	0,082	0,091	0,100	0,185	0,205	0,226	0,160	0,177	0,195
Project 3	0,188	0,208	0,229	0,164	0,182	0,200	0,237	0,264	0,290	0,133	0,148	0,163
Project 4	0,153	0,170	0,188	0,041	0,045	0,050	0,185	0,205	0,226	0,027	0,030	0,033

Fuzzy PIS and Fuzzy NIS (see Table 4).

Table 4.

Fuzzy PIS and NIS

	Contract Period			Resection in degree of contractor			Project risks			Profit		
Project 1	0,205	0,227	0,250	0,164	0,182	0,200	0,158	0,176	0,193	0,213	0,236	0,260
Project 2	0,170	0,189	0,208	0,082	0,091	0,100	0,185	0,205	0,226	0,160	0,177	0,195
Project 3	0,188	0,208	0,229	0,164	0,182	0,200	0,237	0,264	0,290	0,133	0,148	0,163
Project 4	0,153	0,170	0,188	0,041	0,045	0,050	0,185	0,205	0,226	0,027	0,030	0,033
Possitive ideal	0,205	0,227	0,250	0,164	0,182	0,200	0,158	0,176	0,193	0,213	0,236	0,260
Negative ideal	0,153	0,170	0,188	0,041	0,045	0,050	0,237	0,264	0,290	0,027	0,030	0,033

Compute the distance (see Table 5)

Table 5.

d_i^* and d_i^-

	d_i^*	d_i^-
Project 1	0	0,4895023
Project 2	0,21789442	0,2716079
Project 3	0,19610498	0,2933974
Project 4	0,43072153	0,0587808

The closeness coefficient CC_i (see Table 6).

Table 6.

CC_i

	CC_i
Project 1	1
Project 2	0,554865424
Project 3	0,599378882
Project 4	0,120082816

Stage 6. Ranking (see Table 6)

Table 6.

Ranking		
	CC_i	Rank
Project 1	1	1
Project 2	0,554865424	3
Project 3	0,599378882	2
Project 4	0,120082816	4

First alternative-is the best.

3. CONCLUSION

Project management ensures that the actions necessary for the realization of a project are carried out in accordance with the predetermined conditions; It is done to understand this before any problem arises and to take corrective measures. During this process, studies in different fields of expertise should be carried out regularly and systematically, and resources should be used appropriately. Project management should not be viewed as a mere discipline-based engineering, logistics and construction work, a scheduling and cost control software application.

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